

Pension of Elderly in India: A Sociological Perspective

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Abstract

India is undergoing a remarkable demographic transition, when peeped into elderly population—connoted as aged 60 and above and in most likelihood seems to reach 347 million by 2050. This scenario leads to presents unusual challenges for social policy in ensuring financial security, material security, food security with dignity for elderly citizens. Pensions, as safety net through financial mechanisms are to be visualised beyond it. It is to be seen as engraved into sociological constructs that encapsulates societal values, intergenerational relationships with institutional bearings.

This review paper traces the pension system in India through a sociological lens. It goes at length to examine how going beyond the given threshold of age as determined intersects with caste, class, gender, rural-urban divide along with emphasis on changing family structures. It evaluates the present pension schemes such as the National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP), Employees' Provident Fund (EPF), and Atal Pension Yojana (APY), underlining their constraints to reach the target and exclusions. This review builds on theories like structural functionalism, conflict theory, and symbolic interactionism and tend to analyse how pensions can shape the identity, self-reliance and roles of the senior citizens.

This paper also tends to rely on two diametrically opposite case studies from Kerala and Uttar Pradesh to highlight regional variances and difference in effectiveness of policy. It wraps up with recommendations for a universal policy that includes all and at the same time being sensitive to the culture in which it has to be effective that integrates health, community support, and digital access. By using the lived experiences of India's elderly, this paper argues for a change from fragmented welfare to a holistic vision of plight of elderly.

Key Words: Pension, Elderly, Policy, Health, Community

Introduction

Indias demographic scene is rapidly changing and evolving. With ever rising quality in healthcare, nutrition and life expectancy causing the proportion of elderly mass on steady rise. According to the India Ageing Report, 2023 (UNFPA) the elderly population marked at 149 million in 2022 and in all probability to be more than double by 2050. This demographic shift has serious implications for social policy, especially in a region where informal employment dominates and traditional family support systems are eroding.

Historically, Indian society strongly rely on joint families to care for the elderly. The elderly were dignified as custodians of wisdom and tradition, often occupying pivotal roles in decision-making and child-rearing. However, the process of modernization, flow of urban migration and the rising number of nuclear families have disrupted these arrangements. Today, many elderly individuals live alone or in old-age homes challenged by emotional isolation and financial insecurity.

Pensions are a vital component of elderly welfare programmes providing a safety net against living below poverty line and living independently. Yet, India's pension system is distorted, with multiple schemes targeting different populations but failing to achieve universal coverage. Only a minuscule population of the elderly—primarily those in formal employment—receive regular and standard pensions. The vast majority of population especially in rural areas and informal sectors still remain excluded.

This paper seeks to pose the pension system not just as an economic welfare policy but as a sociological phenomenon with deeper humane aspects. It raises a plethora of question like who gets left out and in what ways pensions affect roles and identities of these senior citizens. Further it also questions 'Which are the cultural and structural variables that leads to accessibility of pensions?' By looking deeper into the questions raised here, the paper tends to contribute in a more emphatic way the vision of elderly population reflecting their plight.

Use of Theoretical Framework

Here sociological theories that offer some valuable insights into the role of pensions in shaping elderly experiences. Three key frameworks guide this type of analysis are:

1. Structural Functionalism

This theory, evolved in hands of Emile Durkheim and Talcott Parsons, views society as a system of interrelated parts working together to maintain stability. Aging is seen as ever evolving natural process where older individuals gradually recede from their active roles, making place for younger generations. Pensions paved way for institutional mechanisms that lubricates this transition, ensuring that the seniors can retire with dignity while enhancing social equilibrium.

In India, however, the lack of universal pensions distracts this balance. Elderly individuals, usually continue working in informal sectors due to financial insecurity, challenging the idea of retirement as a normative life stage.

2. Conflict Theory

The next in the series are the works of Karl Marx's conflict theory emphasizing power dynamics and inequalities. It highlights 'how access to pensions is stratified by class, caste, gender and employment status'. Formal sector employees enjoy structured and regular pension benefits, while informal workers, domestic labourers and workers in agriculture are largely outside the access.

This theoretical framework helps explain why schedule caste, schedule tribe and women—especially widows—face systemic constraints to pension access. It also looks into the state's role in perpetuating these inequalities through inadequate policy making and implementation.

3. Symbolic Interactionism

Another group of theoreticians developed (George Herbert Mead and Herbert Blumer), this theory focuses on micro-level interactions and the meanings individuals assign to social roles. Pensions influence 'how elderly individuals perceive themselves and are perceived by others. Receiving a pension can enhance 'self-worth, autonomy, and social status', while exclusion can lead to feelings of 'shame, dependency, and invisibility'.

In India, where respect for elders is culturally important, the lack of ability to contribute financially or access pensions can degenerate traditional roles and identities, producing social alienation.

Trends in Demographic Transition and Aging in India

India's aging population is growing in two ways; one, absolute numbers and two, as a proportion of the total population. The old-age dependency ratio—defined as the number of elderly per hundred working-age individuals—is on rise steadily creating pressure on families and public resources.

The noted key trends include:

1. **Life Expectancy:** It increased from 41 years in 1960 to be more than 70 years in 2020.
2. **Aging as Feminization:** It is also noted that women live longer than men, but often face greater economic insecurity due to lesser workforce participation and widowhood.
3. **Rural Concentration:** It is seen that over 70% of India's elderly live in rural areas, where access to welfare schemes is less, equally true for pensions and healthcare facilities.
4. **Health Burden:** As far as non-communicable diseases like diabetes, hypertension, and arthritis are rampant among the elderly, increasing their financial insecurity and exposed to greater vulnerability.

These trends underscore the need of developing strong pension systems that encapsulates 'inclusive, accessible, and responsive' to the varied needs of India's elderly population.

Pension Schemes in India

India's pension bouquet is characterized by a combination of contributory and non-contributory schemes, each with its own varied eligibility criteria and constraints.

1. National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP)

It was launched in 1995. NSAP includes the Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme (IGNOAPS), which provides ₹200–₹500/month to elderly individuals living below the poverty line. While the scheme aims to support the most vulnerable, the amount is grossly inadequate and varies across states and sometimes it too inaccessible.

2. Employees' Provident Fund (EPF)

It is managed by the Employees' Provident Fund Organisation (EPFO), this scheme covers formal sector workers. In these contributions are made by both employer and employee and this fund is provided for retirement benefits. However, only about 10–15% of India's workforce is in the formal sector, constraining the scheme's accessibility.

3. Atal Pension Yojana (APY)

It was introduced in 2015. The APY targets informal sector workers, giving guaranteed pensions between ₹1000–₹5000 per month based on contributions mix. Despite this its potential enrolment remains low due to constraints on awareness, financial literacy, financial insecurity and trust in government schemes.

4. State-Specific Schemes

There is diversity in schemes related to elderly's pension. In states like Kerala, Tamil Nadu, and Rajasthan provide higher pension amounts and better cover. Kerala, for instance, provides a universal pension of ₹1600 per month, reflecting a higher emphasis on progressive welfare orientation.

Challenges Faced by Elderly

1. **Low Pension Amounts:** In most schemes it is noted that the offer amounts falls far below subsistence levels that is required in old age.
2. **Exclusion Errors:** The eligibility laid are not objectively drawn leading to discrepancies leading to many eligible individuals are discarded in final documentation.

3. **Corruption and Delays:** The heavy hierarchy itself leads to red tapes and sometimes it's very difficult for people living below poverty line to escape these traps which leads to such corruption and delays. Pension disbursement is very often marred by bureaucratic inefficiencies.
4. **Lack of Portability:** Its difficulty also lies in geographical mobility. Migrant elderly lose access to schemes when moving across states.

Sociological Issues and Pension Accessibility

Pension access in India is influenced by 'engrained social inequalities' which are root cause of severe vulnerabilities. It could be seen in caste, class, gender, family and rural- urban divide.

1. Gender Disparities

Women, especially in rural areas, have lower labour force participation and constrained access to formal employment. As a consequence, they are often excluded from contributory pension schemes. Widows are doubly jeopardised and face additional challenges due to patriarchal norms and lack of legal documentation.

2. Rural-Urban Divide

Rural elderly are more likely to work in informal sectors, making them ineligible for formal pensions. Infrastructure gaps, digital illiteracy, and weak local governance further create constraints to access.

3. Caste and Class

Schedule caste and schedule tribe face systemic exclusion from pension schemes. Local power structures often intervene access, with marginalized groups struggling to go through bureaucratic processes. They are often doubly jeopardised; one as lying lowest in hierarchy rung and two, being aged.

4. Family Breakdown

The ever-increasing number of breakdowns of joint families has posed a colossal problem unique to Indian context. This has caused leaving behind many elderly without familial support. In urban areas, elderly individuals often live 'single' or in old-age homes, relying exclusively on state welfare.

These sociological factors creates a deep need for a pension system that is not just economically substantive but socially just.

Health and Financial Vulnerability

Health and financial insecurity are closely intertwined for India's elderly:

1. **Chronic Illness:** There is high prevalence of non-communicable diseases among elderly with ever increasing healthcare costs and falling health the circumstance becomes more vulnerable.
2. **Out-of-Pocket Expenditure:** In most cases elderly lack health insurance, forcing them to spend from limited savings or pensions. This out of pocket creates tremendous pressure on health on non-earner.
3. **Mental Health:** This financial insecurity contributes to varied state of lower mental health causing depression, anxiety, and social withdrawal.

Pensions, when optimum, can solve these vulnerabilities by enabling access to healthcare, nutritious food, and social engagement. However, current pension schemes are doomed with such meagre amount to meet even basic needs.

One Country, Two Opposite Cases

1. Kerala

Kerala stands out as a 'Model for elderly welfare in India'. This state stands out in more than one way i.e. to say with high literacy rates, established local governance and a tale of progressive social movements. At the moment, the state has implemented a near-universal pension system. In 2023, Kerala gives ₹1600 per month to all elderly citizens, irrespective of income or employment history. The scheme is administered efficiently through local self-governments, which maintain recent beneficiary lists and ensure timely disbursement.

Sociologically, Kerala's approach reflects a rights-based 'Model of Welfare'. The elderly are seen not as burden or dependents but as citizens right to dignity and support. Community organizations and neighbourhood also play a great role in elderly care, offering companionship, helping health check-ups and availing recreational activities. This integrated approach reduces loneliness, isolation and give impetus to social participation among the elderly.

2. Uttar Pradesh

In contrast, Uttar Pradesh possesses a more challenging scenario. With a large rural population and lower literacy rates, pension coverage is less and inconsistent. The IGNOAPS scheme is the primary source of support, offering ₹500 per month, now raised to Rs 1000, to eligible aged below the poverty line. However, exclusion errors are too much to be ignored as processual fault due to poor documentation, corruption, and lack of awareness.

Many elderly individuals in this state rely on informal support networks—neighbours, religious institutions or local charities. The breakdown of joint families and migration of earning members to urban areas has left many elderly without caregivers. Sociologically, this reflects a change from familial to need for institutional dependency, but without adequate infrastructure support, the elderly remain vulnerable.

These contrasting case studies found the importance of political desire, administrative capacity and community engagement in shaping lives of pensioners.

Policy Gaps and Challenges

There is plethora of schemes and initiatives, but certain practices have caused India's pension system to generate several structural and operational gaps:

1. Fragmentation

India's pension design is fragmented across central and state governments, with overlapping and inconsistent eligibility criteria laid. This leads to problem of awareness among beneficiaries and inefficiencies in reach.

2. Inadequate Coverage

It is disheartening to note that only about one-fifth of India's elderly receive any form of pension. The vast majority, especially those in informal sector, remain excluded. This is particularly grave when given that over 90% of India's workforce is informal.

3. Low Pension Amounts

It is also noted that most pension schemes offer amounts far below the poverty line even not adequate for two meals. For instance, ₹500 per month now doubled in UP under IGNOAPS is by far less to cover basic needs like food, clothes and shelter. Not to lesser emphasis at this stage cost of medicine

4. Bureaucratic Hurdles

The enrolment processes are often complicated, requiring number of documents, bank accounts and biometric verification. Elderly individuals, especially in rural areas, faces deeper problem to overcome these complex situations.

5. Lack of Portability

In this fast-moving world it's become very difficult to be geographically stagnant. Rather in search of family and employment to exist at organismic level creates pressure. This change in their residence leads to as pension benefits are often tied to residence, making them inaccessible to migrant elderly who move across districts or states.

6. Gender and Caste Biases

Schedule cast schedule tribe and woman face systemic barriers in accessing pensions due to social discrimination, lack of documents and weak institutional mechanism to support.

Addressing these gaps need a shift from a targeted welfare model to a universal rights-based approach that recognizes elderly as a social responsibility.

Recommendations

The recommendation to design a more inclusive and equitable pension system, the following are proposed:

1. Universal Basic Pension

Introduce a flat pension for all elderly citizens as universal pension system, irrespective of income, caste, or employment history. This would resolve exclusion errors and ease administration.

2. Gender-Sensitive Policies

It has been observed that pension policies are gender sensitive so it would be proper to design special provisions for elderly women, especially widows and single women. This could include higher pension amounts, ease of enrolment and community emphasis.

3. Digital Inclusion

Technology has resolved many issues in country like India; with such burgeoning population it has still a far lesser fraction of population than elderly in European and developed countries but the number of elderly may pose such problems that may not be easily resolved it would be a boon in streamline enrolment and disbursement. So, it would be proper to quickly adopt digital inclusion. Mobile-based applications, biometric verification, and SMS alerts can improve enrolment and disbursement leading to transparency and access.

4. Community-Based Support

Community based support is the need of the hour for elderly as looks helpless amidst losing familial ties and strength to earn. Efficiency of local institutions like panchayats, NGOs, and self-help groups to support elderly welfare can assist with documentation, grievance redressal and social engagement.

5. Integration with Health Services

Health services are often provided separately even to elderly as it becomes more cumbersome. If it is linked to pensions with health insurance schemes like Ayushman Bharat and give regular health check-ups, subsidized medicines and geriatric care through primary health centres can cause relax.

6. Portability of Benefits

The need for the geographical mobility in this era cannot be overlooked. Sometimes elderly member of the family also migrates and at other times they earn their livelihood in a different state or district. To ensure pension benefits across states and districts it requires transfer of pension seamless so that migrant elderly should be able to access their entitlements regardless of location.

7. Monitoring and Evaluation

There is also a need of establishing independent bodies that looks into this pension schemes through monitoring and evaluation as a continuous process, so that the audits and impacts are done in a continuous interval and it could help in fulfilling the identified gaps and improving target groups.

These recommendations are socially responsive and culturally sensitive.

Sociological Reflections

Pensions in India are more than financial security—they are reflections of societal values and priorities. In a culture that traditionally respected the elderly, the current situation of pension exclusion reveals a gap between rhetoric and reality. Elderly is increasingly bestowed with invisibility, dependency and neglect.

From a sociological perspective, pensions can provide basis to ‘dignity, autonomy, and social participation’. They provide the elderly to manage their identity as active not senile and engaged not isolated. Moreover, pensions can boon to intergenerational relationships, reducing the dependence on families and promoting responsibility from elderly side also.

The symbolic value of pensions also cannot be overlooked. It provides a value and worth through which the elderly contribute to the society without being burdensome. It also creates recognition for elderly that generates respect from others. This saves to fall into the group of marginalised.

However, for pensions to perform role at stake, they must be universal, adequate, and accessible. schemes Fragmented schemes and meagre amounts do little to resolve the deeper sociological challenges of aging. A paradigm shift is need of the hour—from welfare to justice and from meagre charity to rights.

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